

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS PART OF END-TO-END DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article describes the technologies that ensure the digital transformation of the economy and society.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, economy, "end-to-end", digital technology, social sphere
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ КАК ЧАСТЬ СКВОЗНЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны технологии, обеспечивающие цифровую трансформацию экономики и общества.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, экономика, «сквозь», цифровые технологии, социальная сфера

Digital technologies are technologies that ensure the digital transformation of the entire economy and society, based on the storage and transmission of information in a digitized format. Artificial intelligence technologies are a group of digital technologies that make it possible to perform tasks that previously required the use of human cognitive abilities (speech and visual recognition, analytical decision-making, complex logical operations, predicting the future based on collected data, etc.) This group of technologies is closely related to other groups of digital technologies called "end-to-end". Currently, a large-scale national program "Digital economy of the Russian Federation" is being implemented in Russia. It was developed in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated May 7, 2018 No. 204 "On the national goals and strategic tasks of the development of the Russian Federation until 2024". approved at the meeting of the Presidium of the Council. Among the tasks of the National Program "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation":

- 1) development and implementation of "end-to-end" digital technologies based mainly on local developments;
 - 2) transformation of the priority sectors of the economy and social sphere, including tax compliance, education, industry, agriculture, construction, urban economy, transport and energy infrastructure, financial services by introducing digital technologies and platform solutions;
 - 3) introduction of digital technologies and platform solutions in the fields of public administration and public service provision, including for the interests of the population and small and medium-sized businesses, including individual entrepreneurs;
 - 4) creation of a system of legal regulation of the digital economy based on a flexible approach in each field, as well as the introduction of civil transactions based on digital technologies, etc.
- The passport of the National Program "Digital Economy of the Russian Federation" was developed by the Ministry of Digital Development, Communications and Mass Media of the Russian Federation, which includes six federal projects: - "Digital Technologies"; - "Regulatory regulation of the digital environment"; - "Information infrastructure"; - "Personnel for the digital economy"; - "Information security"; - "Digital state

administration". The federal project "Digital technologies" is one of the six projects prepared, as we see. It is this project that involves the development and implementation of all "end-to-end" digital technologies. In August 2020, one more project was added to the projects listed above - the seventh "Artificial Intelligence" Federal project approved by the Digital Development Commission under the Government of the Russian Federation. This shows the most important role of artificial intelligence technologies among other digital technologies. Now, with the development of artificial intelligence, other activities should be carried out within the framework of a new project. The development of legal regulation of all technologies is carried out in accordance with the federal project "Regulation of the Digital Environment", which is common to all "end-to-end" technologies. The measures included in each of the seven federal projects allow talking about the digital transformation of all areas of society. Thus, the "Personnel for the Digital Economy" project includes the restructuring of the educational system for the training of personnel who meet the new requirements for the basic competencies of the digital economy, the "Digital Public Administration" project includes public services and services to public services. implies showing. digital format, introduction of end-to-end platform solutions in public administration, and the "Regulation of the Digital Environment" project is aimed at making relevant changes to the legislation and developing new technical standards. Implementation of each of the projects requires extensive use of digital technologies in practice. What is meant by "end-to-end" digital technologies?

These are the main scientific and technical fields that have the greatest impact on the development of markets. This was stated for the first time in the program "National Technology Initiative (NTI)" of Russia. 17- a long-term interagency program of public-private partnership to support the development of new promising markets based on high-tech solutions. According to the text of the "National Technology Initiative (NTI)" program developed in 2016, "end-to-end" digital technologies will determine the development of the Russian and world economy in 15-20 years. End-to-end digital technologies initially included: big data, neurotechnologies, artificial intelligence, distributed ledger systems, quantum technologies, new manufacturing technologies, industrial internet, robotics and sensor components, wireless communication technologies, virtual and augmented reality technologies. These technologies are included in the list available in the first version of the state program "Digital economy of the Russian Federation" in 182017. The program provided for the possibility of changing the list with the emergence of new technologies, that is, the list of "end-to-end" technologies is not closed and may change depending on the level of development of certain technologies and the possibilities of applying solutions. based on these technologies in practice. The federal project "Digital technologies"¹⁹ was developed in 2018-2019 on the basis of the program "Digital economy of the Russian Federation" in connection with the creation of its "successor" - the National program "Digital economy of the Russian Federation", and the following seven groups are classified. "end-to-end" digital technologies:

- 1) artificial intelligence technologies and neurotechnologies;
- 2) components of robotics and sensors;
- 3) virtual and augmented reality technologies;
- 4) new production technologies ("smart manufacturing" technologies (Smart Manufacturing), digital design (Smart Design), additional technologies, etc.);
- 5) distributed ledger systems;

- 6) wireless communication technologies;
- 7) quantum technologies.

For the implementation of the federal project "Digital technologies", roadmaps for the development of each group of such technologies have been developed, since October 2019, seven roadmaps have been posted on the website of the Ministry of Digital Development, Communications and Mass Media of the Russian Federation. The road maps for the development of each of the "end-to-end" digital technologies list the means of supporting the development of the relevant technologies (groups of technologies) at the state level, including by making the necessary changes to the legislation. Despite the fact that only seven groups of "end-to-end" digital technologies are listed in the list, in addition to those listed above, technologies for working with large data (Big Data) and industrial "Internet of Things" technologies (Industry Internet of Things), IIoT) can also be named as such technologies. As mentioned above, these technology groups were included in the list according to the first version of the state program "Digital economy of the Russian Federation" in 2017, in addition, in 2020, along with seven "to the last" groups. "end" digital technologies were named, they were included in the top ten promising technologies. Resolution No. 1750 of the Government of the Russian Federation dated October 28, 2020 regarding these promising technologies. Creation of experimental legal regimes, i.e. intensive implementation in practice formation of the legal basis for The development of "end-to-end" technologies, their introduction into the sphere of production and service is encouraged by almost all countries, because it allows to increase the level of technological development of the country and the competitiveness of the national economy. other countries. Such technologies are the basis of the digital transformation of society, are integrated into all aspects of activity and require large-scale changes in production culture, change the principles of creating products and providing services. At the end of the 20th century, technologies of similar importance were called "disruptive" (Disruptive Technologies or Disruptive Innovations). The term "disruptive innovation" was first used by the American researcher Clayton Christensen in the book "The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail". described the model of the impact of new technologies on the company's activity, which leads to the loss of their positions in the market, because when their products are not competitive, the previously established parameters of competition lose their value. Based on the "end-to-end" name of a number of digital technologies, it is clear that they will not develop in isolation. For example, artificial intelligence technologies are closely related to robotics technologies in that the product is not only a software robot designed to perform a precisely programmed sequence of actions within a process, but also an "intelligent" robot with artificial intelligence. possible The capabilities of artificial intelligence systems and industrial "Internet of Things" technologies make it possible to create "smart" production facilities - Smart Manufacturing - which can work without human intervention or without any participation, as they combine intelligent process control systems and control systems. to unite organizations of any profile into a single structure. It is a fully automated production, and the information received from the sensors is processed by systems using big data technologies. In turn, the development of wireless communication technologies serves to create "smart" productions. The development of artificial intelligence depends on the possibilities of processing large data: the more and "cleaner" the data, that is, the more accurate, the faster the artificial intelligence improves. Advances in quantum technologies are capable of taking large-

scale data processing to a new level and speeding up the machine learning algorithms used to develop artificial intelligence. The development of wireless communication technologies helps to create "smart" productions. The development of artificial intelligence depends on the possibilities of processing large data: the more and "cleaner" the data, that is, the more accurate, the faster the artificial intelligence improves. Advances in quantum technologies are capable of taking large-scale data processing to a new level and speeding up the machine learning algorithms used to develop artificial intelligence. The development of wireless communication technologies helps to create "smart" productions. The development of artificial intelligence depends on the possibilities of processing large data: the more and "cleaner" the data, that is, the more accurate, the faster the artificial intelligence improves. Quantum Advances in technology are able to take the processing of large volumes of data to a new level and accelerate the machine learning algorithms used to develop artificial intelligence. The relationship between artificial intelligence technologies and neurotechnologies is so close that they are often grouped together in digital technology development policy documents. Neurotechnology is a group of technologies that is widely spread in practice due to the development of neurosciences (neurophysiology, neurobiology, neuroengineering, neuroinformatics, etc.). They allow to understand the structure of the brain, to have an idea about the mind, thought processes and higher mental functions. Using neurotechnologies, neurointerfaces are designed to exchange information between the brain and the computer. The future compatibility of artificial intelligence technologies with neurotechnologies makes it possible to predict the creation of human-machine hybrid intelligence.

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